

Direct Water Powered Vehicle

A special vehicle that uses water as a fuel without splitting it into hydrogen and oxygen. It uses water as direct fuel as it is in its original form without making any changes in its compound.

© *Copyright*

Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
08/28/2021